

An analytical study on daily, weekly, monthly and quarterly returns on Indian gold ETFs

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Abstract

Gold is a scarce, precious and costly metal. Women are passionate of jewellery made of gold. It is treated as a financial and a liquid asset. People who invested in gold decades back made huge money. Storing of gold is risky, hence paper gold has taken birth in the market. Gold Exchange –traded Fund (GETF) is a form of paper gold. This is basically an investment fund traded on stock exchanges similar to shares and stocks.

The research study aims to know what gold ETF schemes are yielding good returns on daily, weekly, monthly and quarterly basis so as to guide the investor and the trader and hence they can rotate their fund among different gold ETF schemes offered by different companies to maximize their wealth.

Keywords: Gold, Gold ETFs, Returns, Equity ETFs, Mutual Fund.

Introduction

a) Concept of Gold: Gold is a soft yellow metal. It has highest ductility and malleability of any metal. The physical properties of gold are listed in table 1.

Table 1
Physical properties of gold

Color	Bright Yellow
Luster	It has a shine or glow
Ductility	It can be beaten into extremely thin sheets of gold leaf
Malleability	Capable of being shaped or bent
Conductivity	Good electrical conductor
Solubility	Solubility (ability to be dissolved)
Hardness	A relatively soft metal, gold is usually hardened by alloying with copper, silver, or other metals.
Density	It is a dense metal
Melting point	It melts at 1065°C

Source: <http://www.elementalmatter.info/gold-properties.htm>

As per table 1, the physical properties are good and metal stated features are found in gold and its supply is scarce and hence it is called precious metal and is highly in demand. The features of gold and its preciousness nature made it a costly metal and its supply also is limited. The metal has been used to make variety of jewellery for women. All over the world women are passionate for jewellery, a symbol of femininity and social status. Women feel beautiful and

confident when they wear gold jewellery because it highlights their personality. Marketers have brought many innovative designs and created specific designs for each occasion.

In India the demand for the precious metal has been increasing since civilization. The demand for gold in tones sector wise (types of use of gold) is presented in table 2.

The global demand in tones is presented for the latest 10 years starting from 2010 to 2019 and its break-up according to the purpose in table 2. It is observed that demand for gold jewellery has increased from 2010 to 2013 and later started falling down. Gold use in technology is fluctuated in the beginning and later has been decreasing and hence year on year change is negative. Demand for gold is under cyclical fluctuation registering latest yearly change by 9% increase. The demand from central bank and other institutions is also fluctuating and has shown a minute decrease of year on year for the latest period. The data of table 2 for the four sectoral demands for gold is plotted in the form of bar chart in figure 1.

b) Concept of Gold Investment: Gold is primarily a monetary and financial asset. Everybody shows interest to buy this with an objective of saving money. Hence gold is one of the most preferred vehicles for savings. The special features of gold are:

- i) **It is a timeless and a timely investment:** indicating that investing in gold is always a valid investment and investing any time is also a timely investment. In other words, gold is a safe and anytime investment option.
- ii) **An effective diversifier:** Gold is treated as a portfolio diversifier which means portfolio addition that reduces the overall risk in a portfolio.
- iii) **An ideal gift:** Gift is defined as something given voluntarily without payment in return, as to show favor toward someone, honor an occasion, or make a gesture of assistance etc. Gold is a yellow precious metal and rarely available and a costly item. Hence in a country like India, gifting gold is taken as an ideal gift. In India gold is not only precious but also sacred due to its purity and it is used to make ornaments for deities.
- iv) **A highly liquid investment option:** A liquid investment is any investment that can easily be converted into cash without having a significant impact on its value. Examples of liquid investments are cash, money market funds and shares of publicly held companies that actively trade on an established stock exchange.

Central Bank and official international institutions have been major holders of gold for a long time and are expected to retain large stocks in the future also. The major distinction between trading with gold and regular financial assets such as stocks or bonds is that gold is traded from a “store-of-value” point of view, while financial assets are traded in order to secure future income. In other words, there is scope for more degree speculation in shares and stocks but in gold trading it is less.

c) Merits and Demerits of Physical Gold Investment: The merits of investing in physical gold are presented as follows:

- i) Gold is a more liquid asset; in other words, the investor can sell his gold whenever and wherever he wants to meet his urgent financial needs.
- ii) Gold is one of the best options of portfolio diversifier. Thus, one can minimize the overall risk of the invested portfolio.
- iii) Gold is the one of the most desired commodities due to its physical properties. People feel prestigious to possess the gold.
- iv) Gold is one of the best investment options as it holds its value over a long period of time.
- v) Gold is used as a hedge against inflation by the investors, governments and policy makers.

- vi) Investing in jewellery is nowadays very convenient and fashionable as lot of standard showrooms are selling with Hallmark and keeping innovative designs for each occasion to attract the investors.
- vii) In the form of gold coins and gold bars, there is assurance of purity (24 carats) of the gold.

The demerits of investing in physical gold are presented as follows:

- i) Challenge in storing gold because it is not safe to keep with the investor. To protect it, the investor has to take a bank locker facility which involves cost.
- ii) Gold does not earn a regular monthly income as other investments like 100% secured debentures earn a rate of interest payable quarterly/half-yearly/annually and similarly fixed deposits PPF (public provident fund) etc.
- iii) The market value of gold is subject to market correction, if market rate falls down, the investor will be under losses.
- iv) Jewellery investors have to pay for making charges at the time of buying and in depreciation at the time of sale and keeping at home is risk of theft.
- v) Safety for the gold coins and bars by paying storage charges and lack of denomination leads to slow sale.

Table 2
Global gold demand in Tonnes – sector and year wise

YEAR/ SECTOR/ PURPOSE	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	Year-on-year % change
Jewellery	2,057.1	2,104.1	2,157.2	2,726.1	2,531.5	2,458.5	2,101.1	2,236.9	2,240.2	2,107.0	-6
Technology	460.7	429.1	382.3	355.8	348.4	331.7	323.0	332.6	334.8	326.6	-2
Investment	1,588.0	1,759.2	1,565.5	856.4	913.8	962.3	1,614.5	1,318.1	1,169.8	1,271.7	9
Central banks and other inst.	79.2	480.8	569.2	629.5	601.1	579.6	394.9	378.6	656.2	650.3	-1
Gold demand	4,184.9	4,773.3	4,674.2	4,567.7	4,394.8	4,332.1	4,433.5	4,266.2	4,401.0	4,355.7	-1

Source: Metals Focus, Refinitiv GFMS, ICE Benchmark Administration, World Gold Council

Figure 1: Global Demand for Gold - Sector and Year wise

d) Exchange-traded Fund (ETF): An exchange-traded fund (ETF) is basically an investment fund traded on stock exchanges similar to shares and stocks. An ETF holds assets namely stocks, commodities, or bonds and underlying index. In other words, ETF's price and value depend upon the market value or price of the underlying asset. They are traded with an arbitrage – buying at lower price and selling at higher price or vice versa on the same day with an aim of making profit – mechanism designed to keep it trading close to its net asset value and deviations may or may not occur. When deviation occurs and is favorable to the trader, he makes profit otherwise incurs loss on that day.

ETFs are in many ways similar to mutual funds, but they are listed on exchanges and ETF shares are traded throughout the day similar to ordinary or equity shares of a company. ETFs have so many merits namely low cost, tax efficiency, easy conversion into cash and similar to shares easily tradable, hence they are attractive. Because of this, Exchange Traded Funds (ETFs) are the most popular type of investment options nowadays. An ETF is similar to an index fund but trades like a stock on the stock exchange and hence has better price discovery and liquidity.

The investments on ETFs at global level in trillion US (\$) dollars are presented in table 3. It is observed that the

investments in ETFs all over the world increased from 0.7 trillion USD in 2008 to 4.7 trillion USD in 2018 recording a jump from 100% to 671.43%. But there was no increase in the ETFs investments between 2017 and 2018. The related graph is depicted in figure 2. The graph also shows a straight increase till 2017 and is constant between 2017 and 2018. The expected growth rate of ETF industry at worldwide presented in table 4.

As per the table 4 and figure 3, it is understood that the majority of the respondent-experts of the ETF industry predicted that the industry will grow by 10 to 15% pa for the coming 3 to 5 years

Gold ETFs: Gold ETFs are the exchange traded funds based on the net asset value of the underlying asset that is gold. The Gold ETFs are divided into units representing physical gold. These units may be in paper form or dematerialized form. These units are traded on the exchange like a single stock of a company. Gold ETFs provide the opportunity to the investors to participate in the gold bullion markets without the necessity of taking physical delivery of gold and to buy and sell that participation through the trading of a security on a stock exchange

Table 3
The dollar (\$) amount in trillions invested IN

Year	ETFs Investment	Trend Percentage
2008	0.7	100
2009	1.0	142.86
2010	1.3	185.71
2011	1.4	200.00
2012	1.8	257.14
2013	2.3	328.57
2014	2.7	385.71
2015	2.9	414.29
2016	3.4	485.71
2017	4.7	671.43
2018	4.7	671.43

Source: ETFIGI

Figure 2: World-wide ETF investments

Gold ETFs first started in Canada. The first Gold ETF product launched by name was “Central Fund of Canada”, a closed-end fund founded in 1961. Later the fund was converted into exchange-tradable product to provide investors the ownership of gold and silver bullion. The ETF was listed on Toronto Stock Exchange since 1966 and gold ETF was introduced and listed in American Exchange in 1986. In the name of Gold Bullion Securities, the first gold ETF was launched and listed on 28 March 2003 in the Australian Securities Exchange.

In India, the idea of Gold ETFs was first conceptualized by Benchmark Asset Management Company Private Limited when they filed a proposal with the Securities Board of India (SEBI) in May 2002. After a long gap, they got approved and launched it in 2007. Bang¹ has defined gold ETF as ‘an open-ended mutual fund that invests in standard gold bullion

as its underlying asset’. It is also known as paper gold. Further he asserts that ‘these instruments are listed on the stock exchanges, hence people can buy and sell’. The first ETF was launched in China in 2004. Then after, ETFs have become a key innovation in the Chinese exchange markets and ETFs are mainly in Gold, Silver, Platinum and Palladium⁵. Gold ETF Index Fund is a kind of gold-based asset. It tracks the gold price and each share represents 10 percent of an ounce of gold.

There are different ways to invest in gold as depicted in figure 3 namely i) ETF gold, ii) Mutual fund, iii) E-gold, iv) Gold savings schemes v) Bullion – gold coins, biscuits and gold bars and vi) Gold Jewellery. The pros and cons of investing in gold through different options are clearly mentioned in the figure 4.

Table 4
Compound annual growth rate of ETF industry ahead of 3 to 5 years

Growth Rate	Response in Percentage
Less Than -10%	2.4
-5 to 0.0%	0
No Change	2.4
5-10%	7.1
10-15%	47.6
15-20%	31
20-25	9.5
25-30	0

Source: Global ETF Research 2017

Figure 3: Industry in 3 to 5 years Expected Growth of Global ETF

DIFFERENT WAYS TO INVEST IN GOLD						
	Exchange Traded Funds	Mutual Funds	E-Gold	Gold Savings Schemes	Bullion (coins, bars, biscuits)	Jewellery
PROS	Tracks price of gold; no issue with purity of gold; tax benefits	They invest in ETFs; can use systematic route and in small amounts	Offered by National Spot Exchange, can be converted into actual gold	Purchase gold ornaments via systematic savings with the jeweller	Investor gets gold in its purest form; popular option for gifting	Most popular, albeit indirect form of investment by Indians today
CONS	No systematic investment plans allowed to time the market purchase	Higher brokerage charge than ETFs; dividend option attracts taxes	Needs a separate demat account and broker; not very well-known	Choosing between numerous schemes; checking purity of gold on offer	Expensive route that attracts taxes, storage and insurance costs	Purity problems and tax implications; making charges add cost

Figure 4: Different Ways to Invest in Gold

Source: <https://www.quora.com/What-is-the-best-way-to-invest-in-gold-through-SIP>

Merits of Gold ETFs are viewed by some researchers, for example, Nedeljkovic¹¹ described that Gold ETFs are simple in structure when compared to some other structured products. Further the researcher said that there is no credit risk and investment in Gold ETFs and is very much accessible and simple. They are listed on a stock exchange, quoted in local currency with no minimum investment. The other considerable characteristics of Gold ETFs are their cost effectiveness, security and high liquidity. Carty² also finds out the characteristics of ETFs namely i) flexibility, ii) convenience, iii) risk diversification, iv) tax efficiency and v) cost advantages.

Review of Literature

Kostovetsky⁶ had made a comparative study on performance of the ETFs and Index mutual funds from the investors' perspective and reported his finding that index mutual funds are appropriate for small investors and ETFs large investors.

Yu¹⁶ revealed his research results stating that a substantial amount of the information incorporated into the efficient price of a component stock originates in the ETF market. More interestingly, ETF trades are found to have permanent impacts on component stock prices. An analysis of ETF introductions reveals that both informational efficiency and market liquidity of the component stocks improve after the ETF starts trading.

Madhavi⁸ in her research on Indian ETFs and disclosed that when ETF's fared well at bourses, gold ETFs were also launched by large firms and were listed on stock exchange of India. Further she said that out of the five gold ETFs selected in the study, GOLDSHARE is found to be more correlated to the spot gold price followed by GOLDBEES. Also, she found that the relationship of gold ETFs to Nifty is inverse, indicating that Nifty decreases gold ETFs performed better, which is a unique phenomenon observed mostly in India.

Saleem et al¹⁴ stated certain merits based on research that gold ETF is a very attractive investment destination due to less volatility, no storage risk, available in smaller denominations and less tax when compared to physical gold and equity shares. Raghu¹³ also revealed that gold ETFs provide high returns and always reflect a market position which helps investors gain from the opportunities of the Bull and Bears of the Stock market without the worry of high investments and risks. Naylor et al¹⁰ did a research to examine the difference in the price behaviour of physical gold and paper gold and revealed that the price movements are not in accordance with random walk. They found to exploit the inefficiency as a huge opportunity through a simple filter trading rule.

Goyal and Joshi³ disclosed from their research that the trading of Gold ETFs is different from that of trading equity at NSE. During their study period, the price of gold was rising and creating new highs and hence the trading in Gold

ETFs was increasing. The investors were investing in these gold ETFs to earn a fair and sure profit without taxes and without fear of theft. Further it was found that the variation in prices seemed to very less.

Kurian⁷ studied and found that ETFs forms of investments showed more interest by the investors and said these have much potential in the years to come and once these kinds of investments gain momentum with all its diverse features and huge advantages over mutual funds, then there will be no stopping their growth. Marshall, Nguyen and Visaltanachotic⁹ did research on trading strategies when price disparity led to arbitrage opportunities and explained how the traders be alert and able to encash the opportunity by the use of intraday pair-trading strategies to make good profits.

Kumara¹² has done research for three years period from January 2013 to December 2015 and found that equity ETFs had yielded high returns in two or three quarter but the gold ETFs had incurred losses for all the quarters in the study period. Strydom et al¹⁵ employed various measures of tracking error to test the relative tracking ability of index funds and ETFs which track the FTSE/JSE Top 40 index. They find that ETF's are superior tracking instruments; though there is evidence to suggest that the performance of index funds has improved compared to ETFs over the most study (three-year) period.

Thus, the studies made by different scholars can broadly be classified as follows:

- i) Studies related to features, merits and demerits of general ETFs and gold ETFs
- ii) Performance comparative studies between
 - Gold ETFs and equity ETFs
 - Gold ETFs and Equity stocks
 - Gold ETFs and Stock Indices
 - Gold ETFs and Mutual Funds
- iii) Studies related to trading strategies especially the contexts when and how to make profits on arbitration on daily basis.

There is no study on daily, weekly, monthly and quarterly returns on gold ETFs to know and find the most consistent gold ETF and suggest the appropriate gold ETFs to maximize the returns with minimum risk.

The investor knows that gold ETFs are better than any other mode of investment and there are many schemes being offered by different companies and banks of which what schemes are performing better and which are not doing well.

Similarly, gold ETF schemes are yielding good returns on weekly basis, monthly basis and quarterly basis; it is necessary to know and guide the investor and the trader so that they can rotate their fund among different gold ETF schemes offered by different companies.

Methodology

The framework of the research is discussed as follows:

- i) **Samples:** Gold ETF schemes are introduced by different companies. Here for the study, some of the top-rated gold ETFs are chosen for the study. They are:
 - a) AXISGOLD
 - b) BSLGOLDETF
 - c) GOLDSHARE
 - d) IDBIGOLD
 - e) KOTAKGOLD
 - f) QGOLDHALF
- ii) **Sampling Unit:** The selected gold ETFs are sampling units.
- iii) **Data source and type:** All sources of data are secondary in nature. Mostly the data related to the schemes are extracted from www.nseindia.com.
- iv) **Return (%) Computation:** The following formulae are used to compute the return in percentage:
 - a) Daily return (%) = $\frac{B-A}{A} * 100$
where B is closing price of the ETF on that day and A is opening price of the ETF on that day.
 - b) Weekly return (%) = $\frac{B-A}{A} * 100$
where B is closing price of the ETF on the weekend of the week (mostly Friday) and A is opening price of the ETF on the beginning day of the week (mostly Monday).
 - c) Monthly return (%) = $\frac{B-A}{A} * 100$
where B is closing price of the ETF on the month end of the week and A is opening price of the ETF on the first day of the month.
 - d) Quarterly return (%) = $\frac{B-A}{A} * 100$
where B is closing price of the ETF on the day of the quarter end and A is opening price of the ETF on the first day of the Quarter beginning.
- v) **Data classification and tabulation:** The data collected from www.nseindia.com is classified and tabulated as per the objectives of the study, namely
 - a) Daily returns (%)
 - b) Weekly return (%)
 - c) Monthly return (%) – Month wise and Scheme wise.
 - d) Quarterly return (%) – Quarter wise and Scheme wise.
- vi) **Period of the data:** The data for the selected ETF schemes is collected for 12 months for all the traded days of the latest year 2019.
- vii) **Statistical tools used:** In order to understand the data descriptive statistics namely mean (Arithmetic Mean), standard deviation etc. are applied and to test the hypotheses, ANOVA two-way classification tool is used.
- viii) **Research hypotheses:** The following are the null hypotheses formulated to test them in order to meet the objectives of the research:
 - a) There is no significant difference:
 - Among daily, weekly, monthly and quarterly return on the selected ETF schemes.
 - Among the selected ETF schemes.
 - b) There is no significant difference in the return
 - Among different months.
 - Among the selected ETF schemes.
 - c) There is no significant difference in the return
 - Among different quarters.
 - Among the selected ETF schemes.

ix) Assumptions of the study:

The following assumptions are made:

- a) The computation of return and classification of data is done on the basis of calendar, for example, weekly return is calculated by taking the opening price of the scrip on Monday of that week and closing price of the Friday of that week. If Monday is holiday, the subsequent trading day of that week is considered for collecting the opening price. Similarly, if Friday is holiday in that week, the preceding trading day closing price is considered as the closing price of that week. The same rule is applied in the case of computation of monthly and quarterly returns. In the case of months, calendar months and quarters, January to March are considered for first quarter, April to June, second quarter,
- b) July to September, third quarter and October to December the fourth quarter.
- c) 5% level of significance is assumed for testing of the formulated hypotheses.
- x) **The limitations of the research:** The data is taken for latest one year i.e. for 12 months. This may not be sufficient to know the deeper insights of the price behaviour of the gold ETFs and the behaviour of the investors of gold ETFs.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive analysis of daily returns is presented in table 5. The mean return is negative for all the selected ETFs except for QGOLDHALF scheme but is very negligible. There is no relevance of standard deviation when the return is negative. QGOLDHALF scheme is having 9 times more standard deviation and its distribution is very tall⁴ as its kurtosis value is 33.56 (far greater than +1) and its skewness is -3.259 implying that its distributions is inclined towards minimum or negative zone. On the whole, daily basis for trading purpose ETFs is not yielding, rather the trader will incur loss.

The descriptive statistics for weekly returns is presented in table 6. The schemes like GOLDSHARE, KOTAK GOLD AND QGOLDHALF have positive mean return but in fractions. On weekly basis also the traders will not be able to make profits on the selected gold ETFs.

TABLE 5
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS –DAY WISE

Daily Return	AXISGOLD	BSLGOLDETF	GOLDSHARE	IDBIGOLD	KOTAKGOLD	QGOLDHALF
Mean Return	-0.205	-0.339	-0.027	-0.260	-0.026	0.007
Standard Deviation	0.802	1.386	1.045	1.277	0.796	0.674
Kurtosis	2.716	5.298	41.501	18.141	22.059	33.560
Skewness	0.109	-1.316	-2.389	-2.122	-2.293	-3.259
Range	6.682	10.797	17.130	15.134	9.663	9.139
Minimum	-3.653	-7.284	-9.800	-10.624	-6.798	-6.386
Maximum	3.029	3.513	7.330	4.510	2.866	2.753
Number of Days Traded	245	241	245	242	245	245

TABLE 6
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS –WEEK WISE

Weekly Return	AXISGOLD	BSLGOLDETF	GOLDSHARE	IDBIGOLD	KOTAKGOLD	QGOLDHALF
Mean Return	-0.004	-0.061	0.289	-0.132	0.283	0.310
Standard Deviation	1.538	1.949	1.373	2.279	1.408	1.279
Kurtosis	1.073	7.035	1.571	14.862	0.560	-0.674
Skewness	0.330	-1.781	-0.474	-3.068	-0.203	0.042
Range	8.665	12.269	7.628	15.290	7.189	5.113
Minimum	-3.909	-8.954	-4.216	-12.199	-3.395	-2.156
Maximum	4.757	3.315	3.412	3.091	3.795	2.957
Number of Weeks Traded	52	52	52	52	52	52

The descriptive statistics about monthly returns on the selected gold ETFs is presented in table 7. Surprisingly monthly mean return is positive for all the selected ETFs of which KOTAK GOLD is yielding highest with 2.317% followed by IDBIGOLD (2.168%) and others. Standard deviation (the variation in monthly return) looks same for all the scrips of gold ETFs ranging from 4% to 4.6%. KOTAKGOLD is tall in distribution with a little positive skewness with highest range as its maximum return is found to be KOTAK GOLD.

This implies that the investor should be very cautious in trading or investing on monthly basis. How alert he is, impacts his earnings otherwise the return may fall in the negative zone as the average monthly return ranges from 1.5 to 2.3% only.

The descriptive statistics about quarterly returns on the selected gold ETFs is presented in table 8. In quarterly returns also all the gold ETFs are yielding positive returns. KOTAKGOLD is leading with 7.89% with highest standard deviation (8.5%) followed by IDBIGOLD (6.948%) and then QGOLDHALF, AXISGOLD, GOLDSHARE and BSLGOLDETF. KOTAKGOLD has positive skewness inclining higher rate of returns with its tall distribution.

Therefore, based on the table 7 and table 8, one can imply that the ETFs are good to make a return only if the investor keeps invested for a month or a quarter. In other words, ETFs are not trading platform for daily and weekly trading. Further it implies that the trader or investor has to opt for quarterly investments only to gain more return. On KOTAKGOLD option, monthly return is 2.3% and the same scrip yields 7.9% which is greater than 6.9% ($2.3 \times 3 \text{ months} = 6.9\%$). The comparison of periodical returns with respect to selected ETFs is presented in table 9.

ANOVA two-way is performed on the data to test the 5% level of significance: There is no significant difference: a) Among daily, weekly, monthly and quarterly return on the selected ETF schemes and b) Among the selected ETF schemes.

It is revealed that there is significant difference among the periodical return but there is no significant difference among the selected ETFs. This supports the above stated implication that quarterly returns are sure irrespective of the choice among the selected gold ETFs. The same is visible in figure 5.

TABLE 7
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS –MONTH WISE

Monthly Return	AXISGOLD	BSLGOLDETF	GOLDSHARE	IDBIGOLD	KOTAKGOLD	QGOLDHALF
Mean Return	1.608	1.518	1.816	2.168	2.317	1.884
Standard Deviation	4.180	4.154	4.008	4.607	4.279	4.044
Kurtosis	1.246	0.536	0.681	-0.230	1.717	0.245
Skewness	0.543	0.671	0.423	0.174	0.876	0.428
Range	15.964	14.651	14.627	15.266	15.988	14.330
Minimum	-5.094	-4.288	-4.283	-5.585	-3.685	-4.048
Maximum	10.870	10.363	10.345	9.682	12.303	10.282
Number of Months Traded	12	12	12	12	12	12

TABLE 8
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS –QUARTER WISE

Quarterly Return	AXISGOLD	BSLGOLDETF	GOLDSHARE	IDBIGOLD	KOTAKGOLD	QGOLDHALF
Mean Return	5.584	4.749	5.546	6.948	7.893	5.780
Standard Deviation	4.433	5.675	4.822	8.340	8.507	4.553
Kurtosis	1.388	0.423	0.752	1.664	2.542	1.420
Skewness	0.409	-0.597	0.481	0.663	1.440	-0.086
Range	10.785	13.451	11.567	20.224	19.708	11.135
Minimum	0.499	-2.612	0.179	-2.221	0.342	0.147
Maximum	11.284	10.839	11.746	18.003	20.050	11.282
Number of Quarters Traded	4	4	4	4	4	4

In figure 5, it is clear that quarterly return is far greater than monthly return; monthly return is greater than weekly and weekly return is greater than daily.

The analysis of monthly returns on selected gold ETFs is presented in table 10. The peculiar thing is that in month of August, the return is highest for all the selected gold ETFs. However, KOTAKGOLD is leading with 12.3%. The low rate earner is IDBIGOLD with 9.4%. Further ANOVA is applied to test the hypotheses; there is no significant difference in the return:

- Among different months and
- Among the selected ETF schemes.

It is disclosed that there is significant difference in the return among the calendar months. This implies that investor should be cautious in making investment in gold ETFs as there are certain months incurring loss, as it is told that August is the month giving 10 percent return. Further there is no difference among the gold ETFs.

The analysis of quarterly returns on selected gold ETFs is presented in table 11. The peculiar thing is that in third quarter, the return is highest for all the selected gold ETFs. However, KOTAKGOLD is leading with 20%. The low rate

earner is BSLGOLDETF with 10.8%. Further ANOVA is applied to test the hypotheses; there is no significant difference in the return

- Among different quarters and
- Among the selected ETF schemes.

It is found that there is significant difference in the return among the calendar quarters. This implies that investor should be cautious in making investment in gold ETFs as there is a quarter incurring loss namely first quarter (January to March) where either very low profit or loss is recorded. Further it is observed that third quarter (July, August and September) is yielding more than 10 percent return. Again, KOTAKGOLD is leading with 20% followed by IDBIGOLD with 18% and others. Further there is no difference among the gold ETFs.

Conclusion

Based on the above research results and implications, it can be stated in a nutshell that trading in gold ETFs on daily basis or weekly basis is not advised. One can invest aiming monthly return and quarterly return. Investing on quarterly basis is far better than even monthly basis from return perspective. Further if the investor wants only monthly perspective, July and August are the best two months to yield more return.

TABLE 9
DAILY, WEEKLY, MONTHLY & QUARTERLY RETURNS –SELECTED GETFs – ANOVA

Comparison of Return (%)	AXISGOLD	BSLGOLDETF	GOLDSHARE	IDBIGOLD	KOTAKGOLD	QGOLDHALF
Daily Mean Return	-0.205	-0.3393	-0.0265	-0.2595	-0.0255	0.007
Weekly Mean Return	-0.0042	-0.0605	0.28923	-0.1324	0.2831	0.3096
Monthly Mean Return	1.60817	1.518	1.81558	2.16837	2.3166	1.8843
Quarterly Mean Return	5.5835	4.74851	5.54614	6.94809	7.8928	5.7804
ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	Degrees of freedom	MS	F	P-value	F critical Value
Rows	148.966	3	49.65532	179.6737385*	5.62E-12	3.287382
Columns	3.079614	5	0.615923	2.228666435#	0.105196	2.901295
Error	4.145458	15	0.276364			
Total	156.191	23				

* Significant; # Not Significant

* Difference in periodical returns is Significant

No difference among the selected gold ETFs

TABLE 10
MONTHLY RETURNS –SELECTED GOLD ETFs – ANOVA

Monthly Return	AXISGOLD	BSLGOLDETF	GOLDSHARE	IDBIGOLD	KOTAKGOLD	QGOLDHALF
Jan	3.770	-0.628	3.499	2.779	4.182	4.735
Feb	1.349	2.267	1.226	1.088	1.319	0.239
Mar	-5.094	-4.288	-4.283	-5.585	-3.685	-4.048
Apr	-0.480	-1.078	-0.169	-0.171	1.184	-0.143
May	0.720	2.048	1.540	0.680	0.555	0.897
Jun	4.499	6.458	5.206	5.472	5.395	4.796
Jul	2.721	2.236	3.617	9.682	9.595	3.602
Aug	10.870	10.363	10.345	9.434	12.303	10.282
Sep	-3.166	-3.335	-3.055	-0.684	-2.434	-3.116
Oct	3.355	3.237	3.157	3.215	3.097	4.403
Nov	-2.185	-1.990	-2.392	-3.538	-2.007	-1.918
Dec	2.939	2.927	3.096	3.648	3.697	2.882
ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Square	F Value	P-value	F critical value
Rows	1130.43	11	102.767	62.743*	5E-27	1.967546647
Columns	12.4779	5	2.49558	1.5236 #	0.1976	2.382823301
Error	90.085	55	1.63791			
Total	1233	71				

* Significant; # Not Significant

* Difference in periodical returns is Significant

No difference among the selected gold ETFs

TABLE 11
QUARTERLY RETURNS –SELECTED GOLD ETFs – ANOVA

Quarters	AXISGOLD	BSLGOLDETF	GOLDSHARE	IDBIGOLD	KOTAKGOLD	QGOLDHALF
Jan - Mar	0.499	-2.612	0.179	-2.221	0.342	0.147
Apr - Jun	5.730	6.891	6.171	6.554	6.510	6.141
Jul - Sep	11.284	10.839	11.746	18.003	20.050	11.282
Oct - Dec	4.820	3.876	4.088	5.456	4.668	5.551
ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	Degrees of freedom	MS	F - value	P-value	F critical value
Rows	643.579	3	214.526	46.144*	8E-08	3.287382108
Columns	25.7352	5	5.14704	1.1071#	0.3974	2.901294536
Error	69.7363	15	4.64909			
Total	739.05	23				

* Significant; # Not Significant

* Difference in periodical returns is Significant

No difference among the selected gold ETFs

Figure 5: Comparison of Periodical Return – GETFs

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(Received 17th January 2020, accepted 18th February 2020)